

ISic4373

Dedication by a curator of the res publica Liparitanorum

Language

Latin

Type

Honorific (?)

Material

Marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Giulio Vallarino

Contributors

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Autopsy

2016 (Vallarino)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Found in secondary deposition during excavations in the summer of 2015 in the western part of the area of the 'Hellenistic-Roman temple'

Coordinates

37.298238, 13.589125

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

A slab of white marble, broken into six joining fragments, with only the left margin partially preserved

Dimensions

Height 50.5 cm

Width 48 cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

The remains of six evenly spaced lines of Latin letters are preserved, with a regular left margin; the right margin is not preserved for any line

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are well cut in a relatively refined v-cut, with modest serifs. The letters tend towards the tall and narrow and are very regular and evenly spaced. P and R are open, O is somewhat ovoid, E has bars of equal length, D is quite full, the diagonal of the N does not always start from the top of the first hasta. Interpuncts are not consistently used, with one elegant example in line 2

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 65 mm

Interlineation

Line 1-2: not measured mm

Text

□

1. □us(vac.undefin)o[---]
2. □çur(ator) · rei · p[ublicae]
3. Lip[ar]itanoru[m][---]
4. in omnibus pe[---]
5. a splendidissi[moordine]

6. muneris sui[--- ---]

Apparatus

Text of Vallarino with very minor adjustments

Translation (en)

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Vallarino, G. 2017. L'epigrafe dall'area del Tempio ellenistico-romano. In Calìò, L.M., Caminneci, V., Livadiotti, M., Parello, M.C., Rizzo, M.S.(eds.), *Agrigento. Nuove ricerche sull'area pubblica centrale*. Rome. pp. 123-126.

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Image courtesy of Giulio Vallarino